

STAGES OF OLD AGE NURSING CARE IN MAINTAINING ELDERLY HEALTH

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Annotation: The article will talk about the physiology of youth and how important it is in a person's life, as well as the stages of old age and methods of caring for them.

Key words: old age, physiological, old age, development, immunity, healthy, pathology, fading , normal

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Human life is the period from birth, which includes growth, development, maturity, aging and dying.

from birth to death is called the life cycle. The life cycle of a person means the successive alternation of periods of growth, development, decline and extinction in his life activity.

Growing up is growing up and maturing

Development is a state of growth of physical and mental characteristics or the process of gradual adaptation of the subject to the external environment in the course of life activities.

When we talk about "development", the quality of growth is first of all important. The process of human development has its own direction and sequence. The direction of development serves to ensure that a person lives better than his usual way of life . The sequence of development is not only a time frame, but it is considered an element for the transition from one stage of development to another, it has a clear order and interdependence. So, how to determine the period of old age in general?

As adopted at the 1963 World Health Organization seminar on the aging process held in Kiev:

45 to 59 years old - middle-aged;

60 to 74 years old - elderly;

75 to 89 years old - senior citizens;

90 years and older are considered long-lived

Human development is characterized by successive passing through each developmental stage, starting from birth. Therefore, every stage passed after birth is important for a person

Old age is a legitimate final stage of life. However, premature aging is a fact of life. For this reason, SP Botkin and II Mechnikov were right when they supported the concepts of the existence of physiological and premature aging. Premature aging is characterized by a somewhat early development of age-related changes due to experienced diseases or harmful factors of the external environment. Physiological aging is determined by maintaining mental and physical health, a certain level of work ability, laziness, and interest in the surrounding events. The influence of the external environment and the internal factors of the organism lead to the acceleration of the aging process, premature aging of the organism, this process begins after the growth and development of the organism has stopped. "Gerontology" is closely related to medical biology, which studies the causes of aging of the whole organism, from molecules and cells. Aging is aging, that is, the process of legally occurring changes that occur in the body with age. In general, today, various fields of science that comprehensively study the problems of aging have appeared and are developing rapidly.

Aging is a stage of the body's age. changes in organs and tissues during the aging process are influenced by the external environment. changes in old age are a physiological process , which, according to most scientists, is not considered a primary disease, but leads to a limitation of the body's functional capacity and a decrease in resistance to external harmful factors. The last stage of old age is senescence, which is the result of a functional deficiency caused by internal and external influences during a person's life. In addition, aging is a biologically degradable process , in which the body's ability to adapt becomes limited, various pathological changes develop, and the inevitability of death accelerates. Complex multicellular organisms experience certain changes not only anatomically, but also functionally during their lifetime . These changes are also reflected in their appearance or their habitus as they age . in old age, the skin of the face is dry, wrinkled, shriveled, wrinkled, pale, and as a result of its thinning, the veins under the skin appear bulging. The hair on the head is gray and sparse, the eyes are dull, the teeth are missing in the mouth, the spine is more or less bent, the movements are weak and difficult. These are signs of aging . Vision and hearing decline in old age, and an old person often squints. Height and weight are also reduced. Between the ages of 50 and 85, men decrease by at least 3 cm, and women by 4 cm. Normally, body weight is at its maximum in men at the age of 40, and in women at the age of 50 . Due to the regular increase in the world population and the widespread promotion of a healthy lifestyle among people,

people's desire to live a long life and live a healthy life is growing at a much higher rate than in previous years. . In this regard, the need for medical personnel: doctors and nurses, as well as specialists who care for the elderly, is increasing. Nowadays, time demands the development of nursing work as a "science". Today's nurse should be able to give a "Nursing Diagnosis" to the patient based on the symptoms of the disease. Being able to hear and understand the pain of old and elderly patients, to be able to enter into human communication with them, to feel full responsibility towards the patient and to change his health in a positive direction is the demand of the day. V. Henderson, one of the American theoreticians who raised nursing to the level of science and industry, said that the unique task of medical nurses is to help a person, a healthy person or a patient, restore, strengthen, and live their lives peacefully. believes that it consists of having skills and knowledge. So, the goal of nursing in gerontology is:

1. elderly and the elderly.
2. Achieving the health, maintenance and restoration of the elderly and elderly.
3. Achieving self-care for the elderly and elderly.
4. for a person (elderly) who has reached the end of his life or is suffering from a serious, incurable disease to live his life peacefully.
5. and develop a healthy lifestyle for the elderly .

a special type of nursing thinking and action. Because caring for and treating the elderly requires a special responsibility, culture, and knowledge from nurses. In gerontology, it is necessary for a nurse to work systematically in solving the problem of an elderly person. The nursing process is a dynamic, growing and changing process. Elderly, old people or sick people have a lot of pain. Therefore, the attitude towards their care should be multifaceted accordingly. In other words, the elderly care plan is constantly changing depending on the situation. This process is embodied in their needs. Therefore, the care plan is based on the basic needs of such patients. The nursing process is a goal-oriented, flexible process. The work of a nurse is carried out in hospitals, families, nursing homes, polyclinics. In this process, the nurse needs to use her professional knowledge, talent, experience and logical thinking ability to restore the patient's health, take care of him, and solve his problems. The nursing process in gerontology consists of 5 stages:

Step 1. Data collection, analysis and evaluation. This is done to identify the person's problems and plan care. At this stage, monitoring the patient's

condition consists of collecting information from himself, his relatives, acquaintances, and his medical card. No conclusions are drawn on the information collected at this stage. But in order to know the patient's problem, along with the objective and subjective symptoms of the disease, the main need of the patient is determined. So, in communication with the patient, in order to know his basic needs, we should use comprehensive specialist communication. In gerontology, communication is a communication between an elderly or an elderly patient and a nurse, which involves knowing the patient's mental experiences in a non-personal way, identifying ways to eliminate or alleviate them if they have a negative impact on health, and psycho-emotional peace around the patient. is to create and maintain. A nurse should follow the principles of professional communication when communicating with an elderly or geriatric patient.

In this:

1. Address clearly and clearly in communication.
2. Active listening - being able to listen to the patient's pain.
3. Using questioning techniques.
4. To create a calm, peaceful environment that invites elderly and elderly patients to talk - to share their pain.

Based on the mental and emotional state of the elderly patient, communication is conducted in the direction that interests them more. For this, it is necessary to actively apply the rules of hearing.

1. With appearance (nod, confirmation).
2. Using words that continue the thought. For example: - What happened then? - Is it okay for you?
3. To care, to feel care.

Pay attention to facial and body movements when speaking.

5. In order to solve the anxiety-problem of elderly and old people, it is necessary to repeatedly identify and learn its essence. For this, it is necessary to use verbal (through words), non-verbal (through actions) type of communication.

When a person gets older, he gets a lot of life experience. Such people have the ability to learn from the nurse's communication about themselves and information about the nurse. In communication, 30% of information is expressed in a sentence. 7% is learned from the word, 13% from the tone, 10% from the content. 70% can be recognized by appearance: hands, face, body movements, even smell.

correctly use the method of asking questions in communication .
Questions are asked in three different directions.

1. Closed questions - questions that do not require an explanation. Example: Did you sleep well today? - Yes or no.
2. Open questions - questions that require explanation. Example: - Why couldn't you sleep well today?
3. A guiding question is a question that prompts the thought to continue. Example: - Maybe the weather has affected? Therefore, the rule of asking questions is an auxiliary tool for the deep identification of the patient's problem. At all stages of the nursing process, the nurse must follow the principles of communication.

Stage 2. Nursing diagnosis. That is, based on the etiology of the disease and clinical signs, the main problem of the patient is identified and determined. "Nursing diagnosis" is the basis of the nursing process. The goal of nursing diagnosis is to provide an accurate assessment of the patient's population and course of illness. Communicating with the patient means identifying the problems caused by the patient's illness, keeping the patient's observation diary based on this, and organizing the patient's recovery. A nurse should have excellent practical skills along with theoretical knowledge in nursing diagnosis. It is appropriate to use the **MASLOU scale of needs** in determining the patient's problem .

MASLOW scale, the attitude of an elderly or elderly person to his illness or condition, his belief that he will overcome the illness, how he reacts to the passage of physiological processes in general and what affects it, the ability to protect himself from the influence of the external environment , can't get it, needs help, doesn't need it, feels in harmony with society and relatives, or is lonely. Based on Maslow's hierarchy, a person can only pursue the needs of the higher hierarchy when he satisfies the needs of the lowest row of the hierarchy. The hierarchy of needs and demands is arranged from bottom to top as follows:

1. Meeting needs based on vital necessity.
2. Confidence in security, stability, feeling of freedom (money, insurance, family, friends).
3. Satisfy the need for communication with people (loneliness is a big problem).
4. Self-esteem (if the need is not met, a person feels weak and insecure).
5. It is necessary to feel the need to create, rejuvenate, develop (art, sports, creativity).

Step 3. Planning ways to solve the problem. Planning is carried out together with the patient whenever possible. The nurse makes a plan to alleviate the patient's condition, prevent complications of the disease, that is, to solve the patient's health problems, and notes it on the nurse's observation card.

Step 4. Perform the planned task and document it. This is to record the process of care for the patient and transfer the information to the nurse on duty.

Step 5. Evaluation of the final result, conclusion, or assessment of whether or not a positive result was obtained from the work carried out based on the care plan, if necessary, changing the nursing diagnosis, creating another plan based on the new diagnosis, and carrying out the treatment on this basis.

Conclusion

In short, a mature nurse who can meet the requirements of the present time, relying on the science of gerontology, must be an assistant specialist not only during illness, but also in adapting to the physiological aging process and continuing full life activities. It is important for each of us to train specialists who meet the requirements of such times, and also to be active in promoting a healthy lifestyle in the society. Why, as mentioned above, every person goes through different stages of his life, he certainly experiences periods of youth, middle age, old age, old age. Of course, in these times, everyone pays attention to their health and wants to live a decent life. For this reason, it is advisable to always strive for a healthy life, not to walk idly until old age comes, until various diseases and ailments overwhelm a person. In this regard, we are assisted by doctors and nurses, as well as specialists in gerontology.

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